

A short note on the biogeography of the rarely observed Seychelles butterflies

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Introduction

The Seychelles Archipelago comprises 115 islands in the western Indian Ocean, and form the northern most part of the Malagasy biogeographical subregion. The Seychelles can be broadly divided into the northern granitic and southern coral islands (Braithwaite 1984) (Fig. 1). The granitic islands are situated approximately 930 km NE and 1600 km E of Kenya and Madagascar respectively. The southernmost coral islands of Aldabra Atoll lie about 800 km SW of the granitic islands.

Figure 1. The Seychelles Archipelago, with inset map of the Malagasy subregion.

The Seychelles butterfly fauna is considered well-known with there being a large amount of historical and recent work available (Gerlach & Matyot 2006; Lawrence 2014). To date, 39 species and subspecies have been recorded from the Seychelles Archipelago. Approximately 25 % (i.e. nine species and subspecies) of these 39 taxa are known from captures or sightings of single or very few individuals (Table 1; Fig. 2).

By looking at the faunal affinities of these nine butterflies it is possible to determine the most probable origin of these taxa. The granitic island butterflies appear to have most likely originated from continental African stock, while the coral island taxa probably have a Madagascan and/or Comoros origin.

Four taxa require further discussion. *Papilio phorbanta nana* is a Seychelles endemic subspecies known only from a single male and female captured before 1880. This subspecies differs from the nominate subspecies from Réunion by being approximately half the size of *P. phorbanta phorbanta*. The Seychelles individuals were most likely introduced via the establishment of *Citris* species from Réunion in the 1700's (Legrand 1959). *Citris* species are the larval foodplants of the nominate subspecies (Martiré & Rochat 2008). Secondly, *Papilio dardanus* was observed on Aldabra by H. Legrand (1965) on 22 November 1959. It most likely represents either the subspecies *humbloti* Oberthür, 1888 from Comoros or *meriones* Felder & Felder, 1865 from Madagascar, although this remains undetermined as the individual was not captured. Thirdly, the taxonomy the Malagasy *Belenois* species require revision. It has been suggested that *B. grandidieri* is a dry season form of the endemic *Belenois aldabrensis* (Gerlach & Matyot 2006). However, at present both species are considered distinct and that taxonomy is followed here. Finally, *Euploea rogeri* (Geyer, 1837) is only known from two illustrations by Geyer in Hübner (1837), with the type specimen apparently lost. The butterfly is of unknown origin but was suggested by de Joannis (1894) to be from Seychelles. It may be synonymous with the Seychelles endemic *Euploea mitra* Moore, 1858 (Legrand 1965). As there is some doubt as to whether this butterfly actually existed, it is not included in Table 1, but is illustrated in Fig. 2 for historical purposes.

What is interesting here, is the high percentage these rarely observed butterflies make up the total number of taxa recorded from these islands. Whether or not this is the case on other island systems worldwide is unknown and requires detailed knowledge of an islands butterfly fauna. All the taxa listed here, with the exception of *P. phorbanta nana*, are widespread and often considered migratory. Also, in four cases more than one individual was captured. This indicates that these rarely observed butterflies probably represented individuals from ephemeral populations that established and subsequently

Figure 2. a) *Coeliades forestan arbogastes* ♂ b) *Pelopidas mathias* ♂ c) *Papilio phorbanta nana* ♂ d) *Papilio phorbanta nana* ♀ e) *Papilio dardanus* ♂ f) *Catopsilia florella* ♂ g) *Belenois grandidieri* ♂ h) *Belenois grandidieri* ♀ i) *Amauris niavius dominicanus* ♂ j) *Junonia hierta cebrene* ♂ k) *Hypolimnas bolina jacintha* ♂ l) *Hypolimnas bolina jacintha* ♀ m) *Euploea rogeri* ♀ n) *Euploea rogeri* ♀ (paintings a - l by M. Crafford-Venter; paintings m - n from Hübner 1837).

died out on the various islands. The probability of a single vagrant butterfly arriving in Seychelles and being captured are poor at best, although it could potentially happen on an occasional basis.

Islands are well known for their dynamic and often rapid species turnover rates (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios 2007). The ephemeral nature of certain island butterfly populations has important biodiversity conservation implications at a regional scale. Small populations with negligible immigration rates to sustain them are likely to disappear naturally (Fahrig & Merriam 1994). The disappearance of endemic island populations is however more of a conservation concern, with their extinctions more likely due to anthropogenic factors.

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Table 1. Distribution and faunal affinities of the rarely observed Seychelles butterfly taxa. C = Comoros; Ma = Madagascar; R = Réunion; M = Mauritius; A = Continental Africa; O = Orient; SG = Seychelles granitic islands; SC = Seychelles coral islands; X = taxon present in geographic area

Seychelles taxon	C	Ma	R	M	A	O	SG	SC	Notes
Hesperiidae									
<i>Coeliades forestan arbogastes</i> (Guenté, 1863)	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	Two captures (Lawrence 2010)
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	X	One capture (Lionnet 1970)
Papilionidae									
<i>Papilio phorbanta nana</i> Oberthür, 1880	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	Two captures (Legrand 1959)
<i>Papilio dardanus</i> Brown, 1776	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	One sighting (Legrand 1965)
Pieridae									
<i>Catopsilia florella</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	One capture (de Joannis 1894)
<i>Belenois grandidieri</i> (Mabille, 1878)	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	Two captures (Lionnet 1970)
Nymphalidae									
<i>Amauris niavius dominicanus</i> (Trimen, 1879)	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	One capture (Legrand 1965)
<i>Hypolimnas bolina jacintha</i> (Drury, 1773)	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	One capture, one sighting, one unconfirmed sighting (Lawrence 2014)
<i>Junonia hierta cebrene</i> (Trimen, 1870)	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	One capture (Legrand 1965)

Call variation in sooglossid frogs

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The frogs of the family Sooglossidae are restricted to the Seychelles islands, although the isolated and anatomically and genetically divergent Indian frog *Nasikabatrachus sahyadrensis* (Nasikabatrachidae) has been suggested to be a member of the family (Frost *et al.* 2006). Here the conventional usage (e.g. Biju and Bossuyt, 2003; Van der Meijden *et al.* 2007) is followed, restricting the Sooglossidae to four species from the Seychelles islands. Naskibatrachidae and Sooglossidae are sister families and the Sooglossidae are believed to have evolved in isolation in the Seychelles islands through vicariance as the continental plates of Seychelles and India separated round 64 million years ago (Mukhopadhyay *et al.* 2012). Today the diminutive Seychelles frogs are restricted to the islands of Mahé, Silhouette and Praslin (Taylor *et al.* 2012).

The Sooglossidae comprise four species: *Sooglossus sechellensis*, *S. thomasseti*, *S. gardineri* and *S. pipilodryas*. These have recently been divided into two genera: *Sooglossus* containing the two former species and *Leptosooglossus* or *Seychellophryne* containing the latter two. *Leptosooglossus* and *Seychellophryne* were described simultaneously, and despite the uncertainty of the order of precedence of these names, I use *Seychellophryne* for the two smaller species: *S. gardineri* and *S. pipilodryas*. It is thought that these species have diverged sympatrically on the larger islands of the Seychelles group, with recent isolation of populations on different islands due to Holocene sea level fluctuations (Van der Meijden *et al.* 2007). Accordingly it may be expected that inter-population variation (particularly between islands) would reflect a recent history of expanding and contracting ranges, with a close similarity between Mahé and Praslin populations, and a moderate degree of structuring within the topographically complex island of Mahé. The results of the study of call variation are described here.

Methods

Sooglossid calls were recorded in all of the main populations in 2010-12 (Table 1). Locations are marked on Fig. 1. Recordings were made using Song Meter SM2+ (Wildlife Acoustics) and SMXII microphones to record over 24 hours at each site. Files were recorded in uncompressed WAV format. Where possible calls were recorded over a 24 hour period and at different times of year to allow diel changes in calling rates and characteristics to be investigated. The call recorder simultaneously recorded air temperature (to an accuracy of 0.1°C), allowing call characteristics to be compared directly with ambient temperature.

Table 1. Sooglossid calls recorded at different field sites

Island	Site	Species	Number of calls	
			recorded	analysed
Mahé	Morne Blanc	<i>S. gardineri</i>	16,440	202
		<i>S. sechellensis</i>	8,940	58
		<i>S. thomasseti</i>	19	19
	La Reserve	<i>S. gardineri</i>	1,824	89
		<i>S. sechellensis</i>	2,278	123
Silhouette	Gratte Fesse	<i>S. gardineri</i>	28	8
		<i>S. pipilodryas</i>	35	12
		<i>S. sechellensis</i>	3	3
		<i>S. thomasseti</i>	2	2
	Mon Plaisir	<i>S. gardineri</i>	600	21
		<i>S. pipilodryas</i>	53	4
		<i>S. sechellensis</i>	180	18
Praslin	Glacis Noir	<i>S. thomasseti</i>	3	3
		<i>S. sechellensis</i>	1	1

Fig. 1. Location of call recording points and distribution of Sooglossidae. Sooglossid range shaded. 1- Mon Plaisir, 2 – Gratte Fesse, 3 – Morne Blanc, 4 – La Reserve, 5 – Glacis Noir

For each site several calls of each species (numbers varying per site – Table 1) were analysed. Analysis was carried out using Song Scope Bioacoustics Software V4.0 to determine call and note duration, frequency range, dominant frequency of primary and secondary notes, number of primary and secondary notes, note structure (frequencies pattern and number of pulses). Where calls from different sites overlapped in characteristics the significance of any differences were analysed using a t-test.

Fig. 2. Typical calls of *Sooglossus gardineri* and *S. pipilodryas*

Results

The four species were easily distinguished on recordings by their call frequency and structure (Fig. 2-4; Table 2-3). Due to its geographical restriction and relative scarcity (Gerlach 2011) fewest calls were recorded of *S. thomasseti*, with three calls from Mon Plaisir (Silhouette) and 18 from Morne Blanc. This does not allow geographical

Fig. 3. Typical calls of *Sooglossus sechellensis*

variation in this species to be evaluated. *S. pipilodryas* is restricted to Silhouette island and the distribution of the species suggests that there is a single population, with any structuring being unlikely. Nonetheless comparison can be made between two sites (Gratte Fesse and Mon Plaisir). *S. gardineri* was recorded in abundance at all sites on Mahé and Silhouette and comparative analysis was undertaken. *S. sechellensis* was recorded in all Mahé and Silhouette sites and is also the only species present on Praslin. Only a single call was obtained from that island. The results of call analysis are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 4. Typical calls of *Sooglossus thomasseti*

Table 2. Call parameters and analysis, values are means with ranges in parentheses

species	Call type	Site	N	Full call	Duration	Primaries	number	duration	frequency	pulses	number	frequency
<i>gardineri</i>		Morne Blanc	42	178 (80-344)		1			5347 (4855-5900)	-	-	-
		La Reserve	189	218 (82-387)		1			4840 (4461-5287)	-	-	-
		Mon Plaisir	21	170 (56-362)		1			5202 (4725-5727)	-	-	-
		Gratte Fesse	8	295 (160-346)		1			5468 (5028-5719)	-	-	-
		Mon Plaisir	4	3984 (3471-4622)		6.0 (5-7)	78		4578 (3471-4778)	-	-	-
<i>pipilodryas</i>		Gratte Fesse	12	4142 (3144--5232)		6.0 (5-8)	110		4863 (3184-5232)	-	-	-
		Morne Blanc	23	711 (368-1104)		1	152		2969 (344-1104)	144 (142-167)	4.0 (1-6)	2470-4484
<i>sechellensis</i>	Full call	La Reserve	26	542 (56-1014)		1	79		2846 (2470-4095)	481 (320-647)	5.5 (3-10)	2388-4207
		Mon Plaisir	6	887 (187-391)		1	316		2792 (2583-3292)	50-60	4.9 (2-7)	2583-4052
		Gratte Fesse	2	1002 (1000-1003)		1			2528 (2130-4310)	81 (62-100)	4.5 (4-5)	2129-4427
		Glacis Noir	1	1656		1	365		2730	142	9	2228
	Primary only	Morne Blanc	35	164 (68-280)		1	164		3141 (2220-4484)	102 (71-167)	-	-
<i>thomasseti</i>		La Reserve	26	357 (56-763)		1	357		3274 (2962-3538)	500 (480-550)	-	-
		Mon Plaisir	11	311 (256-384)		1	311		2795 (2600-2905)	50-60	-	-
		Gratte Fesse	1	329		1	329		2652 (2203-4250)	59	-	-
	Full call	Morne Blanc	14	4921 (1760-7624)		3.1 (2-4)	2749		1028-1918	500-600	9.3 (4-13)	976-2030
		Gratte Fesse	2	2342 (1902-2781)		2.0 (2)			1639 (1006-1954)	?	6.0 (5-7)	958-1855
Primary only	Morne Blanc	9	1707 (48-1000)		1.8 (1-3)			1312 (968-1832)	200 (125-250)	-	-	
	Mon Plaisir	3	1492 (981-2769)		4.7 (4-8)			1676 (1270-2220)	50 (30-71)	-	-	

Diel variations in calling rates are shown in Fig. 5. *S. thomasseti* was only recorded at dusk (18:00hrs) and at night, *S. sechellensis* showed a crepuscular peak in calling rate but was active at all times, although only at low levels at night. *S. gardineri* and *S. pipilodryas* were largely diurnal.

Fig. 5. Diel variation in calling rates at different sites. Top to bottom: La Reserve, Morne Blanc and Mon Plaisir. *S. sechellensis* and *S. thomasseti* on left axis and *S. gardineri* and *S. pipilodryas* on right. Nighttime hours shaded.

S. gardineri

There is little variation in these simple calls. Duration varies by 323 ms and calls are longest at the lower altitude sites (La Reserve and Gratte Fesse), due to few short calls. Frequency also follows an altitude pattern with lower frequency calls at lower altitudes, although this pattern is not statistically significant. There is no statistical correlation between frequency and duration.

In most sites there was no correlation of call duration or frequency with temperatures. At the high temperature site of Gratte Fesse call duration was correlated with temperature ($y=98.06x-2138.8$, $R^2=0.10$). Taking the data overall there is a correlation between temperature and duration ($y=10.83x-52.18$, $R^2=0.12$) and a much weaker correction between temperature and frequency ($y=21.35x+4755.5$ $R^2=0.07$). Short, high frequency calls are produced in the cooler sites.

S. pipilodryas

No significant differences were found in the two field sites occupied by this species. Although these calls sound superficially similar to those of *S. gardineri* (the latter lacks the characteristic repetition of *S. pipilodryas*) the primary notes are significantly shorter and lower frequency than those of *S. gardineri* (30-196 ms. compared to 64-387 ms and 3184-4863 Hz compared to 4472-5900 Hz), thus they are not simply a repetition of the *S. gardineri* call.

S. sechellensis

Two types of call were recorded: single calls (lacking secondary notes) and full calls (one long primary call followed by one or more short secondary notes). Single calls were slightly longer than the primaries of full calls but did not differ significantly in terms of structure of frequency characteristics.

Full call duration was slightly longer at higher altitudes, with significantly longer primary calls. This is due to local temperature effects as total call duration was positively, but weakly, correlated with temperature ($y=47.35x-598.7$, $R^2=0.15$) and primary call duration strongly affected by temperature ($y=35.77x-548.56$ $R^2=0.54$).

Call frequency (both for primaries and secondaries) was highest at Morne Blanc and lowest at Mon Plaisir, but variability was also greatest at Morne Blanc and a comparison of the two sites does not identify any significant differences. Frequency was also not correlated with temperature; frequencies were highly variable below 21°C

Table 3. Significant differences between sites, using two-tailed t-tests with unequal sample size and variance

t-test	Sites compared	Call characteristic	duration		
			T	df	P
<i>gardineri</i>	Mon Plaisir –Gratte Fesse	Duration	-3.7602	13	<0.05
	Mon Plaisir – Gratte Fesse	Frequency of primaries	-2.4228	11	<0.05
<i>sechellensis</i>	Mahe – Silhouette	Frequency of secondaries	9.2672	58	<0.001
<i>thomasseti</i>	Mahe – Silhouette		5.3834	23	<0.001

with very little variation above this temperature. The number of secondaries showed a clear altitude relationship, with the greatest number at the lowest sites, but this was not correlated to temperature. Pulse rate in the primary call did show geographic variation with 50-60 pulses per second at Mon Plaisir, 58-100 (mean 82) at Gratte Fesse, 142-167 (mean 144) at Morne Blanc, 320-647 (mean 481) at La Reserve and 142 on Praslin.

Single calls at Morne Blanc occurred at all hours, being predominant in the early morning (06:00-08:00hrs) and late afternoon (15:00-16:00) (Fig. 6). Between these times calls were scarce and multiple. At Mon Plaisir calling was more restricted, at 6:00 and 19:00, single calls dominated the former and formed 50% of the latter. At La Reserve singles were present throughout the survey, dominating at 15:00.

S. thomasseti

The full call of this species recorded at Morne Blanc and Gratte Fesse. Calls lacking secondary notes were longer at Morne Blanc than at Mon Plaisir but not significantly so. Comparing isolated primaries with the primaries of full calls shows that full primaries are longer than the isolated calls. Primary frequencies of full calls are relatively low. The number of primaries is greatest in the full call.

Pulses in the primary notes varied from 30.3-250/second, with Mahé having 91-250 (mean 174.97) and Silhouette 30-71 (mean 49.67), suggesting that there is geographical variation in this feature although the available data are limited.

Discussion

This analysis of sooglossid calls confirms previous descriptions for the four species (Nussbaum *et al* 1982; Gerlach & Willi 2002). Geographical variation in calls is very limited with some evidence of differences in call duration, frequency and the number of secondary calls in species with complex calls. However, characteristics such as pitch, repetition rate and duration are known to be affected by temperature and would therefore be expected to vary with local climate. The correlation with temperature was significant for duration, frequency and number of secondaries, but explained only a small proportion of the variance. This can probably be explained by the temperature data being recorded as ambient temperature for the site, and not temperature at the calling point (as has been the case for most studies: Zweifel 1959). If it had been possible to record temperatures at the exact calling point a more precise relationship may have been identified. Pitch and repetition rate are positively correlated with temperature (Wong *et al.* 2004) whilst duration and inter-call interval have negative correlations with temperature (Schneider 1974; Lingnau & Bastos 2007). Not all characteristics vary; pulses per call does not change (Schneider 1974) and these patterns are most apparent in advertisement calls, being obscured when frogs are duetting or chorusing (Wong *et al.* 2004). Therefore pulses may show more meaningful geographical patterns than pitch or timing. For *S. sechellensis* some geographical variation was found with distinct pulse rates on Silhouette (50-60 pulses/second), north Mahé (144) and south Mahé (448). The single call from Praslin had a value within the range of north Mahé (142). *S. thomasseti* was recorded at 175 pulses/second. Nussbaum *et al.* (1982) recorded similar values from north Mahé: 157-206 and 107-124 respectively.

Fig. 6. Proportions of single and multiple calls at different sites. Grey – multiple notes, white – primary note only. Top – La Reserve, middle – Morne Blanc, bottom – Mon Plaisir. Only full calls were recorded at Gratte Fesse.

The number of secondary calls in *S. sechellensis* could not be explained by temperature, although there was a significant negative correlation between altitude and the number of secondaries. Many frogs have different advertisement and territorial calls; in the case of *Rana clamitans* these have been divided into Type I “advertisement call” (Wells, 1978) and a longer call with less distinct harmonics (Ramer *et al.* 1983), the Type II “high intensity advertisement call” (Wells, 1978) or “territorial call” (Littlejohn, 1977). The Type I call is thought to be an advertisement call that enables location of calling individuals. The Type I is an agonistic signal to intruders (Ramer *et al.* 1983). Similarly to *Sooglossus sechellensis* and *S. thomasseti*, *R. clamitans* produces single- and multiple-note versions of its Type I calls. The multiple-note version varies from 2-5 notes, successively decreasing in amplitude (Ramer *et al.* 1983). The normal call is the Type I and this is almost the only call produced by small males (Ramer *et al.* 1983). Large males are more active callers than small males and produce most of the multiple-note calls (Ramer *et al.* 1983). In the single-note call the dominant frequency is negatively correlated with caller size, allowing size evaluation by intruders (Ramer *et al.* 1983) and seems to be an advertisement call revealing the location of a calling male. The multiple-note call is an agonistic version and is suggested to be used in non-directed calling by territorial frogs (Ramer *et al.* 1983). Distinct single- and multiple-note calls (2-10 notes) are also produced by the leptodactylid frog *Eupsophus emiliophuini*. Again, single-note calls predominate. These have a lower intensity than the advertisement calls (Penna *et al.* 2005) and are produced during short-range encounters between males, appearing to be agonistic (Penna *et al.* 2005). It appears that single-note calls are simple advertisement calls whereas multiple-note versions are used in close-range agonistic encounters. This is supported in *Sooglossus* by observations of captive frogs where males kept with females only produced single-note calls, and not the apparently agonistic multiple-note calls (pers. obs.). Courtship is generally simple, with females responding to the advertisement call, which conveys size information in its dominant frequency. Accordingly the number of multiple-note calls is expected to be related to population density, which is supported here by the greatest number of multiple-note *S. sechellensis* calls being recorded in the high density population of Morne Blanc. The number of secondary-notes or repeats is correlated with body size in at least some species (Richardson *et al.* 2010), making this a useful characteristic in size selection in agonistic encounters. This also means that locality differences in call repeats may be due to local differences in size or age of males. At Morne Blanc the number of secondary notes varied from 1-6 with a mean of 4.0, a higher number of notes was recorded at Mon Plaisir (2-7, mean 4.9). A higher number again was recorded at La Reserve (3-0, mean 5.5). This may indicate that males were larger (older) at lower altitudes than the higher altitude ones, which are dominated by younger males. This may be the result of greater breeding success at higher altitudes, giving a younger profile. Such a pattern is to be expected as wetter higher altitude conditions would result in longer breeding seasons and, hence, the potential for higher recruitment.

The only geographical variation in calls that could not be attributed to local differences in temperature or population age structure identified for any sooglossid was the pulse rate of the primary call in *Sooglossus sechellensis*. This formed three distinct

groups: Silhouette, north Mahé and south Mahé. A single call from Praslin grouped with those from north Mahe. It has been suggested (Taylor *et al.* 2010) that some frogs on Praslin had been introduced from Mahé, which may explain this result. These three call groups may reflect geographical isolation of the three populations (see Fig. 1), studies are currently underway to investigate the level of genetic isolation of these populations. Complexity of the call of *S. thomasseti* is comparable to that of *S. sechellensis* but data on that species is insufficient to determine whether or not there are geographical variations in calls of that species.

The lack of geographical pattern in the smaller sooglossid species (*Leptosoglossus/Seychellophryne*) is in marked contrast to some other species of frog where local variation in call is known (e.g. Wycherley *et al.* 2002). This may be due to as yet unexplored local temperature or demographic factors in these frogs, or may indicate a constrained aspect to the calls of small sooglossids. Their vocalisations are relatively simple, and extremely so in the stereotypical call of *S. gardineri*. Although durations and frequencies are variable they only vary by 440% and 11% respectively. One of the notable features of the Sooglossidae is that they lack middle-ears, thus the normal auditory pathway is absent. Sound transmission is thought to occur through the palate rather than through the (absent) ear (Boistel *et al.* submitted). This is most effective with high frequency sounds, with the size of the animal being negatively correlated to the detectable frequency. Accordingly the smallest species (*S. gardineri*) has the highest pitched and narrowest range call. This acoustic limitation may mean that almost all components of their calls are functional and cannot drift to produce geographical variation.

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A first assessment of elasmobranch catch in Mauritian artisanal fisheries using interview surveys

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Abstract: Elasmobranchs face severe overexploitation worldwide and data to support effective fisheries management are lacking, particularly for artisanal fisheries. There is a dearth of information on Mauritian fisheries and nothing is known about elasmobranch catches in the artisanal sector. Artisanal fishers (n=92) were interviewed across Mauritius island, to assess the basic characteristics and magnitude of the elasmobranch fishery. Elasmobranchs were targeted using lines and were caught incidentally in nets, but whatever the intent of the catch, sharks and rays were almost always retained to eat or sell. Eleven elasmobranch species were recorded including Sphyrnidae, Carcharidae, Lamnidae, Rhinobatidae (*Rhynchobatus djiddensis*) and Myliobatidae (*Manta* spp). It appears that Mauritian industrial fisheries were responsible for significant shark mortality from the late 1990s until the early 2000s, resulting in severe declines. Currently, elasmobranchs are rarely caught by artisanal fishers and there is no major market for shark fins in Mauritius.

Keywords: bycatch, Chondrichthyes, Mauritius, rays, sharks, small-scale fisheries

Introduction

Over recent decades, the shark fin trade has transformed elasmobranch fisheries from low-value to extremely high-value and c. 63 - 273 million sharks were fished annually between 2000 and 2010 (Worm *et al.* 2013; Eriksson & Clarke 2015). Elasmobranchs are generally long-lived, slow-growing and late-maturing with low fecundity and their fisheries must therefore be managed conservatively (Hoening & Gruber 1990; Musick *et al.* 2000; Baum & Myers 2004; Barker & Schluessel 2005) However, elasmobranch fisheries are typically data-poor and shark populations are widely reported to be in serious decline (Castro *et al.* 1999; Baum *et al.* 2003; Ward & Myers 2005; Dulvy *et al.* 2014). Many elasmobranch species, especially sharks, are apex predators, and changes in their abundance may adversely affect species in lower trophic levels (Heupel *et al.* 2014; Hussey *et al.* 2015).

At the global level, most elasmobranch catch is taken by industrial fisheries, but the impact of artisanal fisheries is also likely to be extensive, particularly in developing countries (Bonfil 1994; Jacquet & Pauly 2008; Oliver *et al.* 2015). Artisanal fishers

generally focus on nearshore waters, which are important for a number of shark and ray life-history stages (Knip *et al.* 2010). Even when elasmobranchs are not directly targeted by artisanal fisheries, they are often still a valuable component of the catch; in reality, sharks and rays are often more accurately considered as secondary targets rather than waste (Kroese *et al.* 1995; Dulvy *et al.* 2008). The informal nature, geographical inaccessibility, diverse gears and wide range of species that are caught in artisanal fisheries make them particularly difficult to monitor and regulate (Pilling *et al.* 2008). However, fishers' knowledge can provide a useful tool to rapidly collect information on a fishery to advise management efforts (Moore *et al.* 2010; Daw *et al.* 2011).

Mauritius is a small island nation located in the western Indian Ocean, c. 800 km to the east of Madagascar (Figure 1). Although the fisheries sector is not a major contributor to Gross Domestic Product or national employment, artisanal fisheries are important at the local level, both culturally and for coastal livelihoods (Paul 1987; Hollup 2000; Vogt 2001; Sobhee 2004). The country's Exclusive Economic Zone is extensive, spanning Mauritius, Rodrigues, St Brandon (Cargados Carajos Shoals) and Agalega, covering an area of 1.9 million km². Mauritian fisheries include industrial (national and foreign fleets), semi-industrial, small-scale commercial, artisanal fleets and recreational fishers (Everett & van der Elst 2010). Mauritian artisanal fishers employ gillnets, large nets, basket traps, lines and harpoons from small fiberglass motor boats in the lagoon on fringing reefs and other nearshore areas around Mauritius and Rodrigues (Ministry of Agro Industry, Food Production and Security 2008). The main groups targeted include Serranidae, Siganidae, Lethrinidae, Lutjanidae, Scaridae, Mullidae, Mugilidae, Acanthuridae, octopus and lobsters (Paul 1987).

Artisanal elasmobranch fisheries are widespread in the western Indian Ocean region but reliable data on the scale of these fisheries are limited (Marshall & Barnett 1997; Smale 2008). Preliminary assessments of shark and ray fisheries have been conducted for the island groups of Chagos (Graham *et al.* 2010), Madagascar (McVean *et al.* 2006; Doukakis *et al.* 2011; Robinson & Sauer 2013) and Reunion (Poisson 2011). The Republic of Seychelles has developed a national plan of action for shark conservation (Nevill *et al.* 2007) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission collects basic data on the magnitude of shark bycatch in industrial, semi-industrial and more recently, artisanal fisheries (Indian Ocean Tuna Commission 2015). However, there is a paucity of data relating to marine fisheries in Mauritius (van der Elst *et al.* 2005; Everett & van der Elst 2010). This study aimed to provide a first assessment of the basic characteristics and magnitude of artisanal elasmobranch fisheries in Mauritius.

Materials and Methods

Elasmobranch catch in Mauritian artisanal fisheries was evaluated using structured interviews of fishers and evaluation of existing fishery data. A total of 11 out of the 61 official landing sites on Mauritius island were sampled (Figure 1). Sites were selected to achieve a geographically representative sample using stratified sampling with strata based on the number of fishers registered at each site (Ministry of Agro Industry, Food Production and Security 2008). Fishers were questioned about

Figure 1. Mauritius, showing fisher interview sites. Inset shows location in the Indian Ocean. Bracketed numbers indicate number of fishers interviewed at each site.

their boat and gear characteristics, relative frequency of catch for each species, whether elasmobranchs were targeted or caught incidentally, spatial and temporal characteristics of fishing sites, market preferences, uses and trade and local attitudes (approach based on Moore *et al.* 2010). Fishers were selected at random and interviewed individually in Mauritian Creole by a team of students from the University of Mauritius. All fishers interviewed gave their prior and informed consent before interview and were given the option to remain anonymous. Images of elasmobranch species were used to clarify identification discrepancies. A total of 92 interviews were conducted out of the estimated 2,078 artisanal fishers (4.4 %) and 1,570 boats (5.9 %) registered on the island (Ministry of Agro Industry, Food Production and Security 2008).

Results and Discussion

Fishing experience of respondents ranged from 5–70 years (mean = 29.0 years), all fishers interviewed worked at least 2–4 days per week and most went to sea everyday (68 respondents, $n = 92$, 73.9 %). Fishers used boats from 4 m to 12 m (mean = 7.4 m) in length, almost all were motorized (6–100 HP, mean = 17.0 HP). Three main fishing gears were recorded among artisanal fishers: lines, nets and traps; seven fishers also used harpoons as a supplementary gear (Table 1). Lines with 1–20 hooks were the most common gear reported (75 respondents, $n=92$, 81.5 %) and were used in a wide range of habitats, from 0.1 to 45 km (mean = 10.3 km) offshore. Nets were utilized by 16 respondents ($n=92$, 17.4 %), 6–500 m (mean = 330 m) long and with a mesh size of 5–15 cm, deployed 0.3–20 km (mean = 5.8 km) offshore. Traps were used by 54 fishers (58.7 %, $n=92$ and measured 0.7–9 m across, deployed to depths of up to 100 m. Frequency of elasmobranch catch depended on the gear being used, and whether the fisher was actually targeting elasmobranchs or if they were caught incidentally (Table 1). Lines were the preferred gear to target elasmobranchs, and nets were the gear most likely to catch sharks incidentally, with 62.5% of net fishers catching sharks and rays even though they were not actually targeting them (Table 1).

Table 1. Gear distribution for the targeted shark fishery, incidental shark catch and the Mauritian artisanal fishery as a whole (bold text indicates most prevalent gear for each catch category)

	Number of fishers using gear (<i>N</i>)	Number of fishers using each gear who reported	
		Targeted elasmobranch catch	Incidental elasmobranch catch
Longline	75	39 (52.0%)	24 (32.0%)
Trap	54	1 (1.9%)	2 (3.7%)
Net	16	1 (6.3%)	10 (62.5%)
Harpoon	7	-	-

Most of the fishers interviewed (77 respondents, n=92, 83%) had caught sharks and rays, and out of these, elasmobranchs were targeted (41 respondents, n=77, 53.2 %) and caught incidentally (36 respondents, n=77, 46.8 %) in almost equal proportions. Elasmobranchs caught incidentally were nearly always retained, only one fisher stated that they would release them and one preferred to use them as bait; all others sold or ate any shark catch. Shark and ray meat was sold for between 0.18–2.90 (mean 1.35) US\$ kg⁻¹, making it far less valuable than other finfish which retail at 3-9 US\$ kg⁻¹ (Ministry of Agro Industry, Food Production and Security 2008).

Elasmobranch catches were rare: shark fishers stated that they had caught between 0–30 animals (mean = 3.6) during the last year. Catches were widely considered to be most frequent during the austral summer (December – February). Fishers mainly caught sharks and rays in the open ocean (53 respondents, n=77, 69%). Shark fins were only mentioned by one fisher, who noted the value of dorsal fins, indicating that there was no major local market for them in Mauritius at the time. In general, fishers had highly negative feelings towards sharks, and thought of them as dangerous, destructive, man-eaters.

A total of eleven elasmobranch species were reported by shark fishers around Mauritius and there were no obvious differences between species distribution for targeted or incidental catch (Table 2). *Sphyrna* spp. were most widely caught, although they may have just been most commonly reported because of their recognizable features. Elasmobranch catches included a wide variety of Carcharidae, two Lamnidae, the guitar shark *Rhynchobatus djiddensis* and one mention of *Manta* spp. (Table 2). In terms of conservation status, *Sphyrna lewini* and *S. mokarran* are Endangered and catches also included the Vulnerable *Carcharodon carcharias*, *R. djiddensis*, *Isurus oxyrinchus* and *Manta* spp. (IUCN 2015; Table 2).

Table 2. Shark species caught by Mauritian artisanal fishers ordered by frequency of reports and showing conservation status of each species

Species	Number of fishers reporting catches	% shark fishers (n=77) reporting catches	IUCN Red List status ¹
<i>Sphyrna</i> spp.	38	49.4	LC - EN
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	30	39.0	NT
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	13	16.9	NT
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	10	13.0	NT
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	7	9.1	NT
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	6	7.8	VU
<i>Rhynchobatus djiddensis</i>	6	7.8	VU
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	5	6.5	VU
<i>Loxodon macrorhinus</i>	4	5.2	LC
<i>Carcharhinus leucas</i>	3	3.9	NT
<i>Manta</i> spp.	1	1.3	VU

¹IUCN, 2015

Inadequate and misleading reporting of shark catches, particularly in artisanal fisheries is widespread (Bonfil 1994; Clarke *et al.* 2006; Jacquet *et al.* 2008; Boistol *et al.* 2011). Mauritius has submitted elasmobranch catches to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) from 1977-2013, ranging from 0-500 tonnes y^{-1} , with a peak of 309 tonnes in 2003 and only 1 tonne reported in 2013 (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2014). The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) also holds shark catch records in Mauritian industrial longlines from 2001-2008, ranging from 0-309 tonnes y^{-1} ; and in artisanal hand lines from 2011–2013, amounting to 1–3 tonnes y^{-1} (Indian Ocean Tuna Commission 2015). By crudely extrapolating the figures obtained during this study, it is likely that the artisanal fishery in Mauritius is responsible for an elasmobranch mortality of the order of 6,000 sharks per year. Between 1996 and 2011, Hong Kong imported 899,359 shark fins from Mauritius, with a peak of 135,155 fins in 2003 (Clarke 2014); these figures show little correlation with the catch reported to the FAO and IOTC, except for generally increased shark catch and exports in the late 1990s and early 2000s with a peak in 2003.

All shark catches reported by Mauritius to the IOTC were recorded as bycatch (Indian Ocean Tuna Commission 2015) although it is clear from this study that artisanal fishers also directly target elasmobranchs, and almost always retain any shark bycatch. In the current study, net fisheries were found to be the most prevalent gear for incidental captures of sharks, as has been found for several other taxa (Reeves *et al.* 2013; Wallace *et al.* 2013). Shark products are rarely sold locally in Mauritius, except to Chinese restaurants, where shark fin soup is openly available; jaws sell for 20 US\$ each (Clarke & Dent 2014) and fins are also traditionally used by the Mauritian-Chinese community as a treatment for renal illnesses (Mahomoodally & Muthoorah 2014; Mootoosamy & Fawzi Mahomoodally 2014).

Mauritius has attempted to reduce fishing pressure within the lagoon by deploying Fish Aggregation devices (FADs) for utilization by artisanal fishers. Sharks are often a significant component of FAD-associated communities (Taquet *et al.* 2007) and so it is likely that much of the shark catch reported here was caught at FADs although no fishers mentioned FADs during interviews.

A total of 61 elasmobranchs including 43 shark species and 18 rays are known to exist in Mauritian waters (Kiszka *et al.* 2009). This study confirmed that at least 11 species are caught by artisanal fishers, including the guitar shark *Rhynchobatus djiddensis* and *Manta* spp. The species recorded corresponded closely with those caught by artisanal fishers in the neighbouring Seychelles (Nevill *et al.* 2007), but contrasted with Mauritian commercial longliners, which primarily land *Prionace glauca* and *Isurus* spp. as bycatch (Mamode 2011; Beeharry *et al.* 2013). It was surprising that *Carcharhinus longimanus* was not reported, because this species is regarded as abundant in the area (Smale 2008). The threatened status of many of the species reported is also cause for concern.

Mauritius' economy depends heavily on international tourism and pristine marine biodiversity, and the presence of sharks increases the desirability of the destination, particularly for divers (Topelko & Dearden 2005; Sobhee 2006). There are dive sites in Mauritius that historically have a reputation for aggregations of sharks,

including the ‘Shark Pit’ at Flat Island, off Cape Malheureux and ‘Passe St Jacques’ near Le Morne. The frequency of shark sightings at both sites has fallen significantly in recent years, and local divers commonly blame overfishing (Kiszka *et al.* 2009). Declines of sharks at these sites correspond closely with the peak of shark exploitation in Mauritius mentioned previously.

This study suggests that following heavy exploitation of elasmobranch fisheries in Mauritian waters from the late 1990s until the early 2000s, targeted and incidental catches in artisanal fisheries are now a rare occurrence. The low catches and visible disappearance of sharks from dive sites indicates that elasmobranch populations have significantly declined as a result of overfishing. It is now unlikely that any proliferation in elasmobranch fisheries will occur in the near future because sharks are now so rare that a major targeted fishery is unlikely to arise in the artisanal sector, even if demand for shark products increases.

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**Notes on a swimming *Polistes olivaceus* (DeGeer, 1773)
(Hymenoptera, Vespidae, Polistinae) in Seychelles**

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In warmer climates many insect species are attracted by swimming pools especially during sunny and calm days. This is mainly caused by the reflection of the blue sky in the water. Entomologists benefit from this fact, but owners and tourists often consider the floating insects as a nuisance. I have collected many species of Hymenoptera in swimming pools in several countries. As most of them were dead, I never thought about the swimming abilities of Hymenoptera.

This study, which is based mainly on photos and films made with a Canon S110 and a Samsung Galaxy S4, has been carried out at La Roussette Hotel (Au Cap) on the main island Mahé. At approximately 14.55 on 27.04.2015 I observed a male of the Yellow Wasp, *Polistes olivaceus* (DeGeer, 1773) (Vespidae, Polistinae), landing on the water surface in the swimming pool. After swimming at least 65 seconds the male left the swimming pool. The distance was about two metres. As I did not film the whole action, I estimate the time of swimming at 75-80 seconds.

Polistes olivaceus can stay for a certain period above water due to the high surface tension of water in combination with the elongated legs and other body characteristics. The wasp swims mainly with the fore and middle legs, while the hind legs are mostly used like a “manoeuvrable outrigger”. The fore and middle legs are alternately (right fore leg, left middle leg) used for swimming, but only the tarsi and tibiae are immersed briefly in water (Photo 1). In addition the wings are sometimes used to accelerate the speed. Leaving the water near tiles bordering the pool was no problem for the wasp. All legs of one side must be out of the water to climb the vertical tiles, in doing so the wasps bends the abdomen upwards.

Days later I found an apparently dead female of *Polistes olivaceus* floating in the swimming pool. After I had lifted the wasp out of the water with my right forearm, the female started to crawl and flew away shortly thereafter. Unfortunately it was not possible to observe the behaviour of a wasp continuously from landing on the water to death.

Some years ago (24.04.2010) I made a photo of *Polistes olivaceus* landing on a yellow blossom floating in a pool of the Rivière Cascade Victoire on Rodrigues (Republic of Mauritius), but I did not make biological notes.

Polistes olivaceus is a terrestrial predator and does not hunt in the water or on the water surface or carries the prey on the water surface like some spider wasps of the genus *Anoplius* Dufour, 1834 (Pompilidae, Pompilinae), e.g. *Anoplius depressipes* Banks, 1919 (Roble 1985) or *Anoplius eous* Yasumatsu, 1936 (Shimizu 1992).

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Photo 1: Swimming male of *Polistes olivaceus* (DeGeer, 1773) (Photo: M. Madl).

Notes on Hymenoptera of Agalega (Republic of Mauritius), with a supplement to Parnaudeau & Madl (2009): Liste des Hyménoptères des îlots coralliens français et mauricien de l'océan Indien occidental

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I. Notes on Hymenoptera of Agalega

Knowledge of the Hymenoptera of Agalega is mainly based on Mamet (1978). Further contributions have been made by Mamet & Webb-Gebert (1980) and Parnaudeau & Madl (2009). Hitherto 15 species have been recorded from Agalega (Parnaudeau & Madl 2009).

Insects from various parts of the world are on display at the Insectarium of the “La Vanille Réserve des Mascareignes” at Rivière des Anguilles (Mauritius), but the focus is on the fauna of the Malagasy subregion, with particular reference to the Republic of Mauritius. In the show room is a large box containing insects, scorpions and spiders from Agalega arranged by their distribution on the North Island and South Island. The insects are represented by following orders (alphabetically): Blattodea, Coleoptera, Dermaptera, Diptera, Hemiptera, Hymenoptera, Lepidoptera, Mantodea, Neuroptera, Odonata, Orthoptera. The material was collected by O. Griffiths and J.M.P. Siedlecki on 10th and 11th April 2006. Unfortunately it is not possible to study the specimens, because the display case is sealed.

The box contains following species of Hymenoptera: *Xylocopa fenestrata* (Fabricius, 1798) (Apidae, Xylocopinae), *Polistes olivaceus* (DeGeer, 1773) (Vespidae, Polistinae), *Ampulex compressa* (Fabricius, 1781) (Ampulicidae), *Chalybion bengalense* (Dahlbom, 1845) (Sphecidae), *Sceliphron madraspatanum* (Fabricius, 1781) (Sphecidae) and two unidentified species of Ichneumonidae from South Island (Fig. 1) and *Xylocopa fenestrata* and *Polistes olivaceus* from North Island. All species except *Ampulex compressa* are first records for Agalega increasing the number of species to 21.

II. Supplement to Parnaudeau & Madl (2009): Liste des Hyménoptères des îlots coralliens français et mauricien de l'océan Indien occidental.

Platygastridae

Unfortunately the file “Famille Platygastridae” was lost during electronic transmission to R. Parnaudeau. This fact was overlooked by the author during proof reading. The additional catalogue is in French with the abbreviations used in Parnaudeau & Madl (2009: 454).

Famille **Platygastridae**

Sous-Famille **Platygastrinae**

***Leptacis insularis* Masner, 1960**

Leptacis (Leptacis) insularis n.sp.: Masner 1960: 2 (cat.), 6 (tax.), 12 (clé), 23 (descr., Glorieuses).

Leptacis insularis Masner, 1960: Vlug 1995: 36 (cat.).

Distribution: Glorieuses. Endémique.

Formicidae

Currently *Paratrechina bourbonica* (Forel, 1886) belongs to the genus *Nylanderia* Emery, 1906 (LaPolla *et al.* 2010: 127).

A revision of the ant genus *Pheidole* Westwood, 1839 (Myrmicinae) from the Malagasy subregion excluding Madagascar was published by Fischer & Fisher (2013). They synonymized *Pheidole picata* Forel, 1891 with *Pheidole megacephala* (Fabricius, 1793) (p. 332) and recorded following species from Juan de Nova.

***Pheidole decepticon* Fischer & Fisher, 2013**

Pheidole decepticon sp.n.: Fischer & Fisher 2013: 304 (tabl. 1: distr.), 307 (cat.), 308 (fig. 2C), 310 (clé, figs. 7A,B), 316 (descr., Juan de Nova), 317 (figs. 15A-F).

Distribution: Juan de Nova. Présente aux Seychelles (Cosmoledo), aux Comores (Anjouan) et à Mayotte.

Vespidae

The valid name of *Eumenes alluaudi* is *Delta alluaudi* (Perez, 1895).

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Figure 1: Hymenoptera from Agalega, South Island. 1: *Xylocopa fenestrata*; 2: *Polistes olivaceus* (two specimens); 3: *Ampulex compressa*; 4: *Chalybion bengalense*; 5: *Sceliphron madraspatanum*; 6: unidentified Ichneumonidae; 7: unidentified Ichneumonidae.

Table 1: Updated checklist of the Hymenoptera from Agalega.

Family	Subfamily	Species and subspecies
Braconidae	Agathidinae	<i>Disophrys lutea</i> (Brullé, 1846)
Ichneumonidae	unknown	two unidentified species
Formicidae	Dolichoderinae	<i>Technomyrmex albipes</i> (Smith, 1861)
		<i>Anoplolepis gracilipes</i> (Smith, 1857)
	Formicinae	<i>Brachymyrmex cordemoyi</i> Forel, 1895
		<i>Paratrechina bourbonica</i> (Forel, 1896)
		<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (Latreille, 1802)
		<i>Cardiocondyla emeryi</i> Forel, 1881
		<i>Monomorium floricola</i> (Jerdon, 1851)
		<i>Monomorium pharaonis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
		<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (Fabricius, 1793)
		<i>Delta alluaudi</i> (Perez, 1895)
Vespidae	Eumeninae	<i>Euodynerus trilobus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)
		<i>Polistes olivaceus</i> (DeGeer, 1773)
	Polistinae	<i>Apis mellifera unicolor</i> Latreille, 1802
Apidae	Apinae	<i>Xylocopa fenestrata</i> (Fabricius, 1798)
	Xylocopinae	<i>Chalicodoma disjunctum</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
Megachilidae	Megachilinae	<i>Ampulex compressa</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
Ampulicidae		<i>Chalybion bengalense</i> (Dahlbom, 1845)
Sphecidae		<i>Sceliphron madraspatanum</i> (Fabricius, 1781)